

LISTENING IS AN INTEGRAL PART OF COMMUNICATION PROCESS

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Abstract: Listening is used in any verbal communication subjected to different purposes. It is impossible to study and use foreign language without listening skills. This article is devoted to peculiarities of listening comprehension.

Key words: listening comprehension, script, audio and video text, monologue, dialogue, listening practice, linguistic skills, sociocultural skill, interlocutor, teaching listening skill

Listening is ability to accurately receive and interpret messages in the communication process. Listening is key to all effective communication. Apart from that listening is one of the main sociocultural skills, which takes an important place in the development of communicative competence and sociocultural knowledge. Sociocultural knowledge and skills are developed during communication, reading, writing, listening and discussions in a target language. Listening is the ability to identify and understand what others are saying. This includes understanding a speaker's pronunciation or accent, his grammar and vocabulary, and grasping his meaning [6, 287].

All the main language skills: reading, writing, speaking, listening are interrelated. So, it is impossible to develop one particular skill separately from others. Thus, learners should be able to communicate in a foreign language to be understood by native speakers. Teaching listening in a secondary school is aimed at the development of the following listening skills that learners should acquire to understand the main information in authentic expressions of everyday situations, to understand native speaker's spontaneous speech, to extract particular or specific information from audio and video texts of different genres and styles. The guarantee for the development good listening skills may be the development of necessary sociocultural knowledge about the target language country, matching the facts of native and target language culture. They should try to avoid faulty pronunciation, errors in grammar or vocabulary, inappropriate or offending style, otherwise, they confuse interlocutor. It is important for a teacher to have a clear understanding of what listening is, why foreign-language learners have difficulties in it, and what solutions we can find. The burning question is how to fill a gap between peculiarities of listening and up-to-date classroom teaching. Traditionally, much classroom practice consisted of the teacher reading aloud a written text, one or more times,

slowly and clearly, and then asking a number of comprehension questions about it. In such approach much attention is not given to the skill itself, or the characteristics of natural spoken English. There is nothing wrong with this approach in itself, but it could claim to be teaching listening comprehension. There are many current listening materials that can be found in the Internet and brought into the classroom. They manipulate both language and tasks, and take into account a range of skills, listener roles, topics and text types. Such approach will be more useful for learners.

Listening is very motivating for language learners, because it gives them information about current world events and the target culture, and puts them in touch with the world outside the borders of classroom and the school. A capable listener is able to perform these four things simultaneously. The most important aspect in listening is 'comprehension'. 'Comprehension' involves extracting meaning from a text, from participating in a conversation or from listening to a person or people speaking [1,14].

When listening to the recording learners often believe that everything that is said is important. This leads to ineffective comprehension, feelings of fatigue and failure. So, learners need practice in selective ignoring of heard information. The ability to understand the main message is of primarily importance for effective listening in a communicative situation. Need to hear things more than once. When students listen to the types of text such as radio and television programs, audio books, lectures, and so on it is often difficult or impossible for them to stop speakers and ask them to repeat or clarify something they have missed or failed to understand. Foreign language learners tend to read more than to listen, because teachers devote very little time to listening in the classroom that is why it creates a need to listen a passage more than one time.

From pedagogical point of view, it is useful for learners to listen to the same texts more than once. But in real life they often have to cope with 'one-off' listening; and teachers should improve their ability to do so. For this purpose, teachers can use texts with 'redundant' passages in which the important information is presented more than once and not too intensively. Speaker's facial expression, posture, eye direction, gesture, tone of voice enriches the content and implications of what is said. Such items contribute spoken information and facilitate listener's comprehension [5,115].

We should also define such factor as is lack of sociocultural and contextual knowledge of the language studied that creates some difficulties for learners in listening comprehension. First of all, a teacher should classify listening materials from the easy to more difficult ones and use materials according to their level. A teacher also should familiarize students with authentic material as well as former sentences and expressions. From time to time listening material should become more and more complicated and totally authentic. It is important and facilitates listening

comprehension when students are provided with background information and various inputs, such as lectures, films, interviews, everyday conversation, TV programs, storytelling, English songs, and so on. According to Brown and Yule audio texts can be divided into three types: static, dynamic and abstract [2,272].

To static texts they refer texts of descriptive and instructive character; dynamic texts are the texts of narrative character which recount an incident; those that express someone's ideas or beliefs refer to abstract texts. All types of texts present different kinds of difficulties, so, to prevent them three types of input should be provided. One more important feature is to provide feedback on learners' performance and observe students' reaction. Thus, a teacher can keep activities purposeful. It can help fulfill error correction and learners' encouragement. Following students' feedback a teacher is aware how the class succeeds and should be managed [2,274].

Listening exercises are divided into three stages: pre-listening, while listening, post-listening. Each stage contains different types of activities. For example, activities (warm-up exercises) referring to pre-listening stage are discussion, prediction about the topic (based on visuals), brainstorming, games, guiding questions.

While-listening stage may include the following activities: comparing passage with prediction, filling in gaps, repetition of the phrases, completion utterances recorded, monitoring mistakes or differences, search of the information, paraphrasing, information transfer, filling in blanks.

Post-listening exercises are: true/false or multiple choice questions, problem solving, summarizing, jigsaw listening, writing based on listening material – letters, telegrams, messages, postcards, speaking as a final stage of listening activities – interview, debate, discussion, dramatization, role play related to listening material. It is a teacher who can arrange listening process with the help of various pre-listening, while-listening and post-listening tasks so that students were completely engaged and benefit from the listening process. A teacher should try to make listening exercises success-oriented. When students succeed they feel more confident in their listening ability. Students should be aware of listening goal. If a teacher conducts a lesson in a foreign language using audio and audiovisual means, he creates a prototype of foreign environment, approaching learning process to real foreign language communication.

In conclusion, listening takes a significant place in language learning and teaching, that is why it is important for language teachers to help pupils become effective listeners, capture their interest, stimulate their imagination and motivate them. However, listening is to be the most difficult skill for students to acquire. The problem is that students lack skills in listening, motivation and memory retention.

Due to different approaches to language teaching that commonly used today a teacher can motivate learners, help them develop listening skills and cope with challenges.

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